

**EXTRALINGUISTIC ISSUES IN CROSS-CULTURAL
COMMUNICATION: BODY LANGUAGE AND TABOOS**

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Abstract: You can explore the problems that occur in intercultural communication in this article. That is, when you see a representative of another culture, it is thought that when you go on a trip or talk with a representative of another culture of another nationality, it will not always be successful.

Key words: Taboos, body language, extralinguistic issues communicationnationality.

Cross-cultural communication involves communication between individuals from different cultural backgrounds. Extralinguistic issues refer to non-verbal cues and gestures that can affect communication and understanding between individuals from different cultures. Some extralinguistic issues that can arise in cross-cultural communication include:

1. **Body language:** Different cultures may have different norms and interpretations of body language. For example, in some cultures, maintaining eye contact is seen as a sign of respect and attentiveness, while in others, it may be considered rude or confrontational. Refers to the nonverbal signals and cues that we use to communicate with others. These signals can include facial expressions, gestures, posture,

and eye contact. Body language can convey a person's thoughts, feelings, and intentions, often revealing more about their emotions and attitudes than their words alone. It is an important aspect of communication and can greatly impact how we are perceived by others.

2. Gestures: Gestures can vary greatly between cultures and can often be misinterpreted. For example, the okay sign (thumb and forefinger forming a circle) is considered offensive in some cultures.

A gesture is a form of non-verbal communication or non-vocal communication in which visible bodily actions communicate particular messages, either in place of, or in conjunction with, speech. Gestures include movement of the hands, face, or other parts of the body.

Gestures differ from physical non-verbal communication that does not communicate specific messages, such as purely expressive displays, proxemics, or displays of joint attention. Gestures allow individuals to communicate a variety of feelings and thoughts, from contempt and hostility to approval and affection, often together with body language in addition to words when they speak.

3. Proxemics: Proxemics refers to the use of personal space in communication. Different cultures have different norms for personal space, with some cultures being more comfortable with close physical proximity while others prefer more distance. Proxemics is a type of nonverbal communication involving how we deal with the environment around us. Proxemics is defined as the study of the nature, degree, and effect of the spatial separation individuals naturally maintain (as in various social and interpersonal situations) and how this separation relates to environmental and cultural factors. (Merriam-Webster)

4. Facial expressions: Facial expressions can also vary between cultures and may not always convey the same meaning. For example, a smile may be interpreted differently in different cultures. A facial

expression is one or more motions or positions of the muscles beneath the skin of the face. According to one set of controversial theories, these movements convey the emotional state of an individual to observers. Facial expressions are a form of nonverbal communication. They are a primary means of conveying social information between humans, but they also occur in most other mammals and some other animal species. (For a discussion of the controversies on these claims, see Fridlund and Russell & Fernandez Dols. Humans can adopt a facial expression voluntarily or involuntarily, and the neural mechanisms responsible for controlling the expression differ in each case. Voluntary facial expressions are often socially conditioned and follow a cortical route in the brain. Conversely, involuntary facial expressions are believed to be innate and follow a subcortical route in the brain. Facial recognition can be an emotional experience for the brain and the amygdala is highly involved in the recognition process. The Amygdala is the integrative center for emotions, emotional behavior, and motivation.

5. Silence: The use of silence in communication can also vary between cultures. In some cultures, silence may be seen as a sign of respect or thoughtfulness, while in others it may be interpreted as awkward or uncomfortable. Silent communication can be more powerful than words. Here's what it is and how to use it effectively. Communication is the tie that binds human beings together. Without it, our thoughts, ideas, and needs could never be expressed or understood. But communicating involves more than the words we speak. It's actually a complex process involving verbal and non-verbal exchanges that all have one goal — to allow others to understand how you think and feel. Yet, out of all forms of communicating, one of the most powerful is silence. Because sometimes, silence speaks louder than words.

A taboo, also spelled tabu, is a social group's ban, prohibition, or avoidance of something (usually an utterance or behavior) based on the group's sense that it is excessively repulsive, offensive, sacred, or allowed only for certain people. Such prohibitions are present in virtually all societies.

3. Taboos may be prohibited explicitly, for example within a legal system or religion, or implicitly, for example by social norms or conventions followed by a particular culture or organization. Taboos are often meant to protect the individual, but there are other reasons for their development. An ecological or medical background is apparent in many, including some that are seen as religious or spiritual in origin. Taboos can help use a resource more efficiently, but when applied to only a subsection of the community they can also serve to suppress said subsection of the community. A taboo acknowledged by a particular group or tribe as part of their ways aids in the cohesion of the group, helps that particular group to stand out and maintain its identity in the face of others and therefore creates a feeling of "belonging".

4. The meaning of the word taboo has been somewhat expanded in the social sciences to strong prohibitions relating to any area of human activity or custom that is sacred or forbidden based on moral judgment, religious beliefs, or cultural norms.

5 To conclude, it is important to be aware of these extralinguistic issues in cross-cultural communication in order to avoid misunderstandings and miscommunications. Being respectful and open-minded towards cultural differences can help promote effective communication and foster positive relationships with individuals from different cultural backgrounds.

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